

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

HUMAN SKIN-MIMICKING INTEGRATED SENSOR WITH ULTRAHIGH SENSITIVITY FOR MULTIDIRECTIONAL SENSING

Chen Haomin

Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering
Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

CONFERENCE
HOSTS:

CONFERENCE
DESTINATION
SUPPORTERS:

#ICCM22

Outline

1. Introduction
2. Human-skin Inspired Stretchable Three-dimensional Sensor Based on Structure Design
 - In-plane Strain Sensor Based on Anisotropic Porous Conductive Network
 - Interlocked Sphere Based Out-of-plane Pressure Sensor
3. Summary

Outline

1. Introduction
2. Human-skin Inspired Stretchable Three-dimensional Sensor Based on Structure Design
 - In-plane Strain Sensor Based on Anisotropic Porous Conductive Network
 - Interlocked Sphere Based Out-of-plane Pressure Sensor
3. Summary

Conductive fillers

+

Elastomer substrate

=

Flexible Strain Sensors

Physiological Monitoring

Prosthesis

Humanoid Robot

- Big challenge remains: **→ Multidimensional strain detection (both magnitude and direction of multiple stimuli)**

- ❑ Sensors based on 1D or 2D architecture

- Response to finite mechanical deformation (mostly in-plane deformation)

- ❑ Sensors mostly based on **isotropic** structure

- Response **similarly** to mechanical stimuli along various directions due to **isotropic** structure.

Current multidimensional sensors

- Poor at **signal decoupling** or **in-plane strain angle detection**.
- **Sensitivity** and **selectivity** also lagged behind

- Sensors based on porous 3D structure

F. X. Yin et al., ACS AML. (2018)

H. W. Zhang et al., Adv. Funct. Mater. (2018)

Y. Song et al., Chem. Commun. (2016)

- Sensors based on interlocked structure

H. Ko et al., ACS Nano (2014)

H. E. Jeong et al., Small (2018)

K. Suh et al., Nat. Mater. (2012) #ICCM22

Fabrication of Multidimensional Sensor

Multidimensional Strain Detection

➤ In-plane

Anisotropic porous conductive network

➤ Out-of-plane

Interlocked microstructure

Outline

1. Introduction
2. Human-skin Inspired Stretchable Three-dimensional Sensor Based on Structure Design
 - In-plane Strain Sensor Based on Anisotropic Porous Conductive Network
 - Interlocked Sphere Based Out-of-plane Pressure Sensor
3. Summary

Fabrication and Characterization

Effect of precracking strain

- Artificial defects created
- Facilitate crack formation and propagation
- Enhanced sensitivity

Enhanced anisotropy

- Significantly improved sensitivity in P direction;
- Similar piezoresistive behavior in T direction.

Pressure insensitiveness

Sensing Mechanism of PUGA Sensor

Strain increases tunneling resistance *via*:

(i) Tunneling distance; (ii) Conducting paths number

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = \frac{R_{tunneling,1}}{R_{tunneling,0}} - 1 = \left(\frac{N_0 w'}{N w_0} \right) \exp[\gamma(w - w_0)] - 1$$

$$R_{tunneling} = \left(\frac{L}{N} \right) \left(\frac{8hw}{3S\gamma e^2} \right) \exp(\gamma w)$$

(i.) $w = (1 + k\varepsilon)w_0$

(ii.) $N = \frac{N_0}{\exp(A\varepsilon)}$

$$\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = (1 + k'\varepsilon) \exp[(A + \gamma k'w_0)\varepsilon] - 1$$

Parallel to the alignment

Transverse to the alignment

In-plane Bidirectional Strain Measurement

➤ Two intersecting PUGA composite for in-plane bidirectional sensing.

- Remarkable sensitivity ~ 168
- Ultrahigh selectivity ~ 3.68

※ **Selectivity**: the capability to differentiate the loading direction, characterized by the slope between ΔGF and θ

1. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, **2019**, 11, 1294-1302
2. *ACS. Nano*, **2015**, 9, 5929-5936
3. *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **2018**, 28, 1802547
4. *Nano Letter*, **2015**, 15, 5240-5247
5. *Nanoscale*, **2017**, 9, 3834-3842
6. *Nanoscale*, **2018**, 10, 5105-5113
7. *Nanoscale*, **2018**, 10, 14938-14946
8. *Small*, **2018**, 14, 1704232
9. *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **2019**, 1901623

In-plane Bidirectional Strain Measurement

$$\begin{cases} \varepsilon_x = \varepsilon(\cos \theta)^2 \\ \varepsilon_y = \varepsilon(\sin \theta)^2 \end{cases} \xrightarrow{\frac{\Delta R}{R_0} = k\varepsilon} \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_x = \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_{\theta=0^\circ} (\cos \theta)^2 \\ \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_y = \left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_{\theta=0^\circ} (\sin \theta)^2 \end{cases}$$

$$\therefore \theta = \tan^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{\left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_y}{\left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_x}}$$

$\left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_x \rightarrow$ corresponding $\left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_{\theta=0^\circ}$ at same strain, then **strain**

magnitude can be read out from the electrical response curve

when $\theta = 0^\circ$.

To demonstrate the in-plane sensing capability

- 10% strain is applied at 30°
- The experimental result, $\left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_x$ is compared with the theoretical value, $\left(\frac{\Delta R}{R_0}\right)_{\theta=0^\circ}(\cos \theta)^2$

Outline

1. Introduction
2. Human-skin Inspired Stretchable Three-dimensional Sensor Based on Structure Design
 - In-plane Strain Sensor Based on Anisotropic Porous Conductive Network
 - Interlocked Sphere Based Out-of-plane Pressure Sensor
3. Summary

Preparation of PS Sphere Array Template

Sphere diameter controlled by:

- Stabilizer (PVP) concentration
- Stirring speed

Styrene (to St+Solvent)	AIBN (to St)	PVP (to St)	Stirring speed (rpm)	Size (μm)
10%	1.00%	40.00%	200	0.9
10%	1.00%	10.00%	200	1.6
10%	1.00%	2.00%	110	2.6

self-assembly

Tunable microstructure based on PS Sphere

PS sphere array (~1.6 μm)

PDMS negative mold

PDMS positive mold

1st replication, PS removal

2nd replication

Performance and Discussions

- Smaller feature size offer higher sensitivity
- Larger feature size present larger linearity.

- Increases of contact area
- Decreases of contact resistance

Application of Three-dimensional Sensor

➤ Detection of multidirectional in-plane strain

➤ Differentiation between normal pressure and shear

Robot grasping control

Sci. Robot, 2018, 3, 24, eaau6914

Human-cyber interaction

ACS. Nano, 2017, 11, 8, 7950-7957

Multidimensional Sensor

Tactile sensing of prosthesis

Sci. Robot, 2018, 3, 19, eaat3818

- Multidimensional sensor capable of **multiple stimuli differentiation**
- **High sensitivity, selectivity** to in-plane strain
- **Tunable sensing performance** for out-of-plane pressure